

MATERIAL AND ENERGY EFFECTS OF FURTHER UTILIZATION OF LIGHT AND HEAVY OILS FROM FLUID CATALYTIC CRACKING (FCC) UNIT

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Abstract

The Fluid Catalytic Cracking (FCC) process yields, among other products, also the Light Cycle Oil (LCO) and Main Column Bottoms (MCB). Both oils are highly aromatic and have several utilization possibilities. In SLOVNAFT refinery, they can be both sent to the Residual Hydrocracker unit (RHC) as aromatic diluents or, in case of LCO sent to the Gasoil Hydrotreater (GHT) for further upgrade to diesel and MCB can also be used in heavy heating oils production. Due to these several utilization possibilities, the effect of each one on material yields and utilities consumption in the refinery should be examined, in order to provide reliable data for the refinery production planning and optimization software (PIMS). In this paper we study the impact of MCB utilization in the RHC unit on material yields, by means of distillation curves and historical RHC operational data analyses. The positive effect of MCB co-feeding to the RHC unit on the more valuable product yields has been confirmed as well as the fact that the MCB also reacts to both heavier and lighter products at the same time. The most important finding is that the marginal MCB co-processing RHC products yields differ significantly from those currently used in PIMS, the biggest difference being observed in the vacuum distillate yield (>66 % vs. 26.4 % used in PIMS). At the same time it appears that the MCB co-processing significantly lowers the amount of produced fuel gas, thus more material remains in more valuable liquid RHC products. Further analyses are needed to assess the impact of MCB co-feeding on utilities consumption in the RHC unit, as well as to elucidate the effect of LCO addition to RHC feed or its impact on utilities and hydrogen consumption in GHT when co-processed there.

1 Introduction

The Fluid Catalytic Cracking process (FCC) belongs to the most important units in a standard refinery. The technology, firstly been applied in the 1940s, converts heavier feedstock, coming mainly from refinery crude units or vacuum gasoils from vacuum distillation units, into more valuable components, mainly gasoline and olefinic C3 and C4 fractions. In order to produce low sulphur FCC gasoline, the vacuum gasoils are usually hydrotreated in the Vacuum Gasoil Hydrotreater unit (VGH) prior to being sent to the FCC unit.

Feedstock processed at the FCC unit in SLOVNAFT refinery is preheated and then after atomization via feed nozzles enters the reactor riser where it contacts the stream of rising catalyst and lift gas (or water steam). The feedstock evaporates and cracks at 520 to 550 °C and cca 0,2 MPa (g). After a short time (usually no more than a few seconds), catalyst is separated from the reaction mixture and sent to regenerator, where the coke deposited on the catalyst particles is burned off with air, thus restoring the catalysts activity and heating the catalyst to

670 to 730 °C. The regenerated catalyst is circulated back to the reactor. Reaction mixture, leaving the reactor is sent to the main column section, where light cycle oil (LCO) and main column bottoms (MCB) products are separated from the reaction mixture and enough heat is recovered to drive the following separation processes (absorption-desorption loop and several rectifications) that separate the rest of the mixture into gasoline, C4 fraction, propane, propylene and C2 fraction (fuel gas). Excess heat from the main column section plus heat from the regenerator flue gas is utilized for high pressure (3,5 MPa (g)) steam production, that in turn is consumed in condensing turbines driving main process equipment (combustion air blower, wet gas compressor, C3 splitter heat pump compressor) [1].

Cracking oils obtained in the main column section can be further utilized in different ways: a part of the LCO is sent to Residual Hydrocracker unit (RHC) as aromatic diluent for the RHC feedstock, the rest of it is hydrotreated in Gasoil Hydrotreater unit (GHT) and yields diesel. The MCB product either is also sent to RHC unit as aromatic diluent or processed together with RHC vacuum residue to heavy heating oil [2].

The Residual hydrocracker unit (RHC) processes heaviest fractions (mainly vacuum residues from various units), that conventionally would be used for heavy heating oil production, at high temperatures and pressures in the presence of hydrogen and converts them to more valuable lighter products (gasolines and oils) that can be further upgraded to diesel and gasoline. Thus it plays a key role in the economics of the SLOVNAFT refinery [3].

The aim of both LCO and MCB addition to the RHC unit feedstock is firstly to prolong the RHC operational cycle by suppressing process equipment fouling and coking and secondly to increase the RHC feedstock conversion. Due to their high aromatics content (>70 % wt.) the LCO and MCB have the ability to disrupt the colloidal structure of long - chained macromolecules present in the RHC feedstock, thus increasing their catalyst and hydrogen accessibility which in the end leads to its increased conversion. The same effect also suppresses equipment fouling and coking [3,4].

According to long term observations of the unit technologists, the dilution effect of the MCB is obvious, whereas that of the LCO is questionable. Based on the analyses presented later in the text it appears that a certain part of the unconverted MCB remains in the RHC vacuum gasoil stream that joins other VGH feedstock streams. Thus the MCB processing chain partly forms a FCC-RHC-VGH-FCC loop. On the other hand, the LCO almost completely joins the RHC middle distillates that are sent to GHT unit. Therefore, with a certain simplification it can be stated that the LCO in the end joins the diesel pool, whether by being sent to the GHT unit directly, or via the RHC unit. As each of FCC, RHC, VGH and GHT unit has its own specific utilities consumption and product yields, the optimal LCO and MCB utilization must be examined carefully.

It thus lies beforehand that the decision making about the FCC LCO and MCB utilization, incorporated in the production planning process, influences not only the refinery products structure, but also the feedstock processing costs and in the end the refinery profit. Thus it is of crucial importance to use correct values of product yields and utilities costs related to those oils processing in various production units in the production planning process.

2 Aims of the contribution

As already addressed briefly in the Introduction part, the optimal FCC LCO and MCB utilization needs answers to following queries:

1. Quantification of the RHC conversion increase effects of the LCO and MCB;
2. Influence of the LCO and MCB addition to the RHC feedstock on the RHC products quality parameters;
3. Quantification of the FCC-RHC-VGH-FCC looping via the MCB;

4. Quantification of the yields and quality parameters of the GHT product streams stemming from LCO co-processing;
5. Quantification of the material and utilities consumption changes related to all LCO and MCB utilization possibilities.

It must be understood that to obtain complete and throughout reliable answers to all these questions in real life conditions is an impossible task. Nearly all of them would require a dedicated long term experiment incorporating at the same time at least the FCC, RHC, VGH and GHT units. The impacts of varying feedstock quality, products quality requirements, feedstock mass flows changes plus scheduled as well as unexpected production units shutdowns represent just a fraction of problems such experiment would encounter. It is known from real life that such experiments, despite being executed just on a single production unit, often have to be shortened or modified on line due to unexpected problems.

Therefore this contribution seeks to provide only limited-scope answers to some of the queries above and to propose further activities that may lead to additional information acquisition related to them. Thus it may be considered as a first step attempt to evaluate the benefits of optimal FCC cracking oils utilization, that are rather „felt“ than quantified at present.

3 Applied methodic

As there has not yet been carried out a dedicated experiment till present, we firstly focused on the analysis of various products densities and distillation curves. These parameters can foretell, in which fraction(s) the co-processed FCC oils split supposing they behave as inerts in the RHC process.

Distillation curve is a temperature dependence of volumetric percentage of obtained distillate to the volume of original sample. Distillation curves are important composition characterization parameters for various gasolines and higher boiling fractions, where they partly or completely supplant the analysis of distinctive compounds content. Fraction density (@15 °C or @20 °C) is another important parameter, indicating the character of the fraction – higher density indicates higher aromatics content, whereas the lower one indicates its paraffinic character.

Our analysis proceeded with evaluating historical data from „normal“ RHC, GHT and FCC operation provided in the form of daily averages of feed rates, feed composition, product mass flows and utilities consumption. These data not only allowed us to extract the yields structure belonging solely to the MCB co-processed in the RHC unit, but also to assess the related utilities consumption. The comparison of obtained yield structure with the predictions made by distillation curves analysis enables us to draw conclusions about the impact of MCB co-processing in the RHC unit both from yields and utilities point of view. The LCO addition effect could not be reliably assessed by historical data analysis, as its flow rate to RHC varied only modestly. Due to the limited space of this contribution, we further dealt just with the effect of the MCB addition on the RHC yields.

4 Obtained results and their analysis

The following Fig. 1 shows the distillation curves for the study relevant RHC and FCC products and for the FCC feed. By their mutual comparison one can assess the theoretical yields of LCO and MCB co-fed to RHC in case they would behave as inerts: The LCO distillation curve is nearly the same as the distillation curve of the RHC gasoil, thus it can be expected that nearly all LCO would join the RHC gasoil product (with a small part possibly ending in the petroleum stream). The MCB distillation curve mostly resembles that of RHC vacuum distillate, with a small overlap with that of RHC gasoil. Thus a small percentage of the co-fed MCB would join the gasoil stream, but the vast majority would go to the vacuum distillate stream.

Fig. 1 Distillation curves for some RHC and FCC products and for FCC feed [1,2,5]

The RHC vacuum residue stream should neither be affected by the LCO and MCB addition as well as should not be affected the lighter RHC products (gases, gasolines).

The comparison of the FCC feed and MCB distillation curves shows the effect of cracking on FCC product properties – even the heaviest FCC product boils at comparable temperatures to the FCC feed. On the other hand, there is a great difference in FCC feed and products densities, as is documented in Tab 1. Also the differences in LCO vs. gasoil and MCB vs. vacuum distillate (and even vacuum residue) densities indicate their different character – LCO and MCB are strongly aromatic fractions, whereas the FCC feed and RHC products are more paraffinic than aromatic (except the vacuum residue stream).

Tab. 1 Typical FCC and RHC product streams and FCC feed densities [1,2,5]

Stream density @ 15 °C, kg/m ³			Stream density @ 20 °C, kg/m ³			
LCO	Petroleum	Gasoil	FCC feed	MCB	Vacuum distillate	Vacuum residue
960	840 ÷ 860	875 ÷ 890	890 ÷ 910	1100	925 ÷ 940	995 ÷ 1010

Historical RHC operation balance data were filtered to remove non-standard states and also operational states with varying MCB addition were sorted out. At the same time, the basic RHC feedstock rate, as well as co-processed LCO rate was constant, which made the marginal yields analysis possible. Its results are presented in the Fig 2. The slopes of linear data fits represent the

marginal yields of RHC products from the co-fed MCB. As stated earlier, the distillation curves analysis predicted, that only the yields of vacuum distillate and, to a small extent that of gasoil should change with varying MCB rate. However, as is obvious from the figure above, the MCB co-processing influenced the yields of several other RHC products, with the extra consumed hydrogen being negligible. This confirms that the MCB indeed takes part in the hydrocracking reactions in the RHC unit. Following Table 2 sums up the marginal yields due to MCB co-fed to RHC in comparison to the specific RHC yields used for refinery operation scheduling and optimization.

Fig. 2 Marginal yields of RHC products and marginal hydrogen consumption resulting from the co-fed MCB

Apart from observed differences in marginal and specific yields of vacuum distillate and vacuum residue, the most surprising effect for us was the decrease of fuel gas production with increasing MCB co-feed. Such effect is very beneficial, as the fuel gas cannot be utilized otherwise than fuel at present. Thus, instead of producing fuel, the RHC unit produces more material when more MCB is co-fed. The decrease of fuel gas production probably also explains lower marginal hydrogen consumption as hydrogen is utilized more effectively: the unwanted cracking of molecules that form the fuel gas fraction is suppressed.

Though having confirmed the active role of MCB in increased RHC feed conversion, it still remains unclear, whether the MCB itself undergoes any changes. The marginal yield of vacuum

residue of more than 19 % from the co-fed MCB indicates that indeed it does. It must be remembered that MCB is highly aromatic. As an inert, it would pass to vacuum distillate which is routed through VGH unit back to FCC. During prolonged co-feeding of MCB to RHC this material loop would concentrate the MCB aromatics among those production units, leading to increasing material streams density and making them successively harder to process. And, most important, the FCC MCB yield would quickly increase beyond the unit's capacity. This does not happen; although the impact of MCB co feeding to RHC in the form of slowly increasing FCC feed density is known. Its quantification would need a dedicated long term experiment.

Tab. 2 Comparison of obtained marginal yields from MCB co-processing and specific yields used in PIMS [5]. The most important differences are highlighted by bold font.

Product/feed	Marginal yield from MCB co processing, %	Specific yield from total RHC feed (basic feed + LCO + MCB + hydrogen + other minor constituents), %
Hydrogen consumed	0.5	1.7
Fuel gas	-7.08	3.87
Light gasoline	Negligible	1.05
Heavy gasoline	Negligible	5.00
Petroleum	2.98	7.94
Gasoil	19.35	16.20
Vacuum distillate	67.66	26.40
Vacuum residue	19.29	36.50
Other (offgases, sour gases, losses...)	Not analyzed	1.34

It can thus be concluded that at least a part of MCB is converted into other products already in RHC unit. The most probable complex view is as follows: the MCB presence in the RHC feed enables more extensive feed cracking to lighter products (mostly gasoil and vacuum distillate), thereby decreasing the amount of produced vacuum residue from the base feed. At the same time the polyaromatic MCB molecules themselves partly undergo both hydrocracking and condensation reactions. The condensation reactions effectively shift the heaviest polyaromatics from the vacuum distillate to the vacuum residue, therefore we see its positive marginal yield despite the positive MCB effect on the base feed cracking. The lighter ones can be partly hydrocracked, yielding mostly vacuum distillate and gasoil.

5 Conclusions

As demonstrated in this contribution, the utilization of cracked oils from the FCC unit merits attention, due to their impact on the refinery's products structure and utilities costs. The presented case study of MCB utilization in the RHC unit is just a part of a bigger frame that needs to be elucidated successively. A dedicated experiment with changing the MCB feed rate to the RHC unit, supported by daily laboratory analyses, could not only confirm the obtained marginal yields from the historical data analysis, but also provide insight into possible composition changes of the RHC products. At the same time the MCB co-processing costs would be estimated reliably and thus distinguished from the specific total feed processing costs used in PIMS at present. Another similar one, aimed at variable LCO addition could finally put an end to the debates about its role as an effective RHC conversion booster and to quantify whether and to what extent it is chemically reformulated at the same time. Further data are also needed in the case of LCO co-processing in the GHT unit. Finally, the FCC-RHC-VGH material loop has to be investigated more deeply prior any relevant conclusions can be drawn regarding the true FCC oils utilization optimum.

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References

- [1] FCC unit operational manual.
- [2] RHC unit operational manual.
- [3] Žajdlík, R., Gazdík J.: SLOVNAFT LCF Operation experience. Presented at the 45th International Petroleum Conference, Bratislava June 2011.
- [4] Manek, E, Haydary, J.: Modelling of catalytic hydrocracking and fractionation of refinery vacuum residue. Chemical Papers 68 (12) 1716-1726 (2014).
- [5] RHC unit PIMS catalogue.